

Screens vs. Sleep: The Hidden Cost of Excessive Screen TimeAbid Manzoor¹, Adil Abbas², Vanshika Sharma³, Tarun Raikwar⁴, Amit Kumar Verma⁵¹Tutor, Department of Physiology, NIMS Medical College, Jaipur²Tutor, Department of Physiology, MMCMSR, Sadopur Ambala³Tutor Department of Physiology, NIMS Medical College, Jaipur⁴Tutor Department of Physiology, Govt Medical College, Satna⁵Tutor Department of Microbiology, MMCMSR, Sadopur Ambala

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Abstract:**Background:** Sleep is vital for overall health and well-being, influencing cognitive, emotional, and physiological functions. Excessive screen time, particularly before bedtime, has been linked to poor sleep quality due to melatonin suppression and delayed sleep onset. Medical students, with their high levels of stress and frequent digital device use, are at increased risk of sleep disturbances.**Aim:** To determine the correlation between screen times and sleep quality as indicated by Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) scores.**Materials and Methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted at NIMS Medical College, Jaipur, involving 95 adults aged 18-24 years medical students, selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Participants were recruited and their screen time was assessed using a structured questionnaire. They were categorized into three groups: Group 1 (<3 hours), Group 2 (3-6 hours), and Group 3 (>6 hours) of screen time. All participants completed the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) to evaluate sleep quality. The collected data were analyzed using statistical methods to assess the correlation between screen time and PSQI scores.**Result:** Test revealed a significant association between PSQI scores and time spent ($p = 0.00001$). Most participants with lower PSQI scores (0-5) spent 3-6 hours, while higher scores (6-9, >9) were more common in those spending over 6 hours, indicating poorer sleep quality with increased time duration.**Conclusion:** Participants with over 6 hours of screen time experienced significantly poorer sleep quality. This study underscores the negative impact of excessive screen use on sleep among medical students. Reducing screen time, particularly before bedtime, may lead to better sleep quality and overall health in this population.**Keywords:** Screen time, Sleep Quality, Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI).This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Sleep is an essential physiological process that plays a crucial role in maintaining overall health and well-being. It is involved in cognitive function, memory consolidation, emotional regulation, and the repair of various bodily systems [1]. The sleep-wake cycle is controlled by a combination of homeostatic mechanisms and circadian rhythms, which are influenced by factors such as light exposure, physical activity, and hormonal changes [2].

Inadequate or poor-quality sleep has been linked to a variety of negative health outcomes, including increased risk of cardiovascular disease, metabolic disorders, and impaired immune function [3]. Sleep quality can be measured using validated tools such as the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), which assesses subjective sleep quality and disturbances across a range of domains [4]. In recent years, screen time has emerged as a significant fac-

tor affecting sleep quality, particularly among young adults and adolescents. The rise of smartphones, tablets, and other digital devices has led to a dramatic increase in screen exposure, especially before bedtime [5]. Excessive screen use, particularly in the evening, can interfere with the natural sleep-wake cycle by reducing the secretion of melatonin, a hormone responsible for promoting sleep onset [6].

Blue light emitted from screens has been shown to delay the onset of sleep, reduce total sleep duration, and decrease overall sleep quality [7]. In addition, prolonged screen use is often associated with cognitive and emotional stimulation, which can further delay sleep onset and lead to poor sleep hygiene [8]. Several studies have explored the relationship between screen times and sleep disturbances. For instance, a study reported poorly that adolescents

who spent more time using electronic devices had poorer sleep quality, shorter sleep duration, and increased daytime sleepiness [9]. More ever a pilot study found a similar association between screen time and delayed sleep onset among adults [10].

Despite the growing body of literature, there remains a gap in understanding the impact of screen time on sleep quality in specific populations, such as medical students, who often experience unique stressors and lifestyle patterns due to the demands of their academic programs [11]. Medical students are known to experience high levels of stress, irregular sleep patterns, and extensive use of digital devices for both academic and recreational purposes, making them an ideal population for investigating the effects of screen time on sleep.

This study aims to fill this research gap by assessing the relationship between screen time and sleep quality among medical students at NIMS Medical College, Jaipur. Using the PSQI to evaluate sleep quality, we sought to determine whether increased screen time is associated with poorer sleep quality in this population.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Physiology, NIMS Medical College, Jaipur, with a sample size of 95 participants. The participants were medical students aged 18-28 years of either sex. Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee, NIMS University, Jaipur, ensuring that all protocols followed ethical guidelines. All participants provided informed consent before participating in the study.

Participants Recruitment

The medical students were recruited based on convenience sampling, ensuring a diverse representation of both male and female students within the defined age range.

Recruitment was conducted within the department through an announcement, and participation was voluntary.

Participants with pre-existing conditions that could affect sleep quality, such as diagnosed sleep disorders, or those taking medications influencing sleep, were excluded from the study. Additionally, students with a history of psychiatric disorders, substance abuse, or recent major surgery were not eligible to participate.

The inclusion criteria for this study required participants to be healthy individuals without any chronic illnesses or underlying conditions that might interfere with sleep or cognitive function.

Assessment of Screen Time

Screen time was assessed by asking participants to self-report their daily screen usage, which included time spent on devices such as smartphones, laptops, computers, and televisions for academic and non-academic purposes. The self-reporting was done through a structured questionnaire, wherein participants were asked to categorize their average daily screen time across a typical week. The total screen time for each participant was recorded in hours and was used to assign them into different groups based on their reported screen time.

Formation of Groups According to Screen Time

Based on the daily screen time reported by the participants, they were divided into three groups for the study.

- Group 1 (0 - 3 hours): Participants with daily screen time of less than 3 hours.
- Group 2 (3 - 6 hours): Participants with daily screen time between 3 to 6 hours.
- Group 3 (> 6 hours): Participants with daily screen time greater than 6 hours.

These groups were created to facilitate comparative analysis and to determine whether increased screen time had a notable effect on sleep quality.

PSQI Assessment for All Groups

Sleep quality was assessed using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) [12], a validated tool commonly used in sleep research. The PSQI consists of 19 self-rated questions that assess various aspects of sleep quality, such as sleep duration, sleep disturbances, sleep latency, and daytime dysfunction, over the previous month¹³. Each participant completed the PSQI questionnaire, and a global score was calculated for each individual. The PSQI score ranges from 0 to 21, with higher scores indicating worse sleep quality. A score greater than 5 is typically indicative of poor sleep quality.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using statistical software to assess the relationship between screen times and sleep quality. Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated to determine the correlation between screen time and PSQI scores. The Chi-square test was used to assess the association between categorical variables, such as screen time groups and sleep quality scores. P-values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant, and results were interpreted accordingly.

Result

The current study analyzed the relationship between screen time and sleep quality, measured by the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), in a

sample of 95 subjects. The chi-square test revealed a significant association between screen time and PSQI scores ($\chi^2 = 46.192, p < 0.00001$). Detailed descriptions of screen time distribution, PSQI

scores are shown below with the help of Tables and Pie diagrams along with their statistical correlation and association.

Table 1: Frequency distribution of screen time of subjects

Screen Time	n = 95	In %
0 - 3 Hrs.	24	25.3%
3 - 6 Hrs.	45	47.4%
> 6 Hrs.	26	27.4%

Table 1 shows the distribution of screen time among 95 participants. The majority of subjects (47.4%) reported screen usage between 3-6 hours per day, followed by 27.4% who spent more than 6 hours on screens daily, and 25.3% who had screen time limited to 0-3 hours.

Figure 1: Showing PSQI Score distribution among the subjects

As shown in Bar Diagram1: the PSQI scores of participants varied widely. A total of 38.9% had PSQI scores between 4-6, indicating moderate sleep disturbances, while 37.9% had scores

between 0-3, suggesting good sleep quality, fewer participants (15.8%) had scores between 7-9, and only 7.4% had scores above 10, indicating poor sleep quality.

Table 2: Association of PSQI score with screen time by using chi-square test

Category	0 - 3 Hrs.	3 - 6 Hrs.	> 6 Hrs.	Chi-Square Test	P - Value	Significance
0 - 5 Score	22	37	3	46.192	0.00001	Significant
6 - 9 Score	2	8	16			
> 9 score	0	0	7			

Table 2 presents the association between PSQI scores and screen time categories. The chi-square test reveals a significant association ($\chi^2 = 46.192, p = 0.00001$) between screen time and PSQI scores. Notably, 22 participants with 0-3 hours of screen time had PSQI scores in the range of 0-5, while those with more than 6 hours of screen time had a higher likelihood of scoring above 6, indicating poor sleep quality.

Figure 2: Showing the association between PSQI score and screen time

Discussion

The impact of screen time on sleep quality has become a significant concern in today's digital age. Our study aimed to explore this relationship among a sample of 95 medical students, revealing noteworthy insights into how prolonged screen exposure affects sleep quality as measured by the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI). The findings indicate that increased screen time correlates with poorer sleep quality (Table 2 and Figure 2), emphasizing the need for awareness regarding screen usage and its implications on health.

Our results align with existing literature that demonstrates a clear association between excessive screen times and sleep disturbances. For instance, a study by Hale and Guan (2015) [14] found that adolescents with high screen exposure experienced significant reductions in sleep quality and duration.

Similarly, a meta-analysis by Wu et al. (2019) [15] highlighted that increased screen time, particularly before bedtime, correlates with higher PSQI scores and sleep disorders among various age groups. In our study, 27.4% of subjects reported spending more than 6 hours per day on screens (Table 1), and these individuals were more likely to have PSQI scores above 6, indicating poor sleep quality (Figure 1).

Furthermore, the chi-square test revealed a significant association between screen time categories and PSQI scores ($\chi^2 = 46.192$, $p < 0.00001$) (Table 2). This reinforces the notion that certain demographics, such as students, may be particularly vulnerable to the adverse effects of screen exposure. Potential mechanisms underlying our findings

may include the effects of blue light emitted from screens, which can disrupt the circadian rhythm and melatonin production, thereby impairing sleep quality. Studies suggest that blue light exposure in the evening can significantly delay sleep onset and reduce overall sleep duration (Hirshkowitz et al., 2015) [16]. Furthermore, engaging with stimulating content on screens may increase cognitive arousal, making it difficult for individuals to wind down and achieve restful sleep (Custer et al., 2019) [17]. As shown in Figure 2, individuals with screen time greater than 6 hours had PSQI scores of 6 or more, illustrating the potential sleep-disrupting effects of extended screen exposure.

In nutshell, our study underscores the critical relationship between screen time and sleep quality, particularly in a medical student population. Given the significant findings from both correlation and chi-square analyses (Table 1 and Table 2), and their alignment with existing research, it is essential to promote awareness of the negative impacts of excessive screen exposure on sleep. Implementing strategies to limit screen time, particularly before bedtime, could prove beneficial in enhancing overall sleep quality and well-being.

Conclusion

Participants with over 6 hours of screen time experienced significantly poorer sleep quality. This study underscores the negative impact of excessive screen use on sleep among medical students. Reducing screen time, particularly before bedtime, may lead to better sleep quality and overall health in this population.

Authors Contributions:

Abid Manzoor and Adil Abbas contributed to the study's conception and design, as well as data collection and analysis. Vanshika Sharma and Tarun Raikwar assisted with participant recruitment and questionnaire distribution. Amit Kumar Verma contributed to the statistical analysis and interpretation of the results. All authors played a role in writing the manuscript and have read and approved the final version.

Source of Limitations:

This study is limited by the relatively small sample size and its focus on a single institution, which may not represent broader populations. Additionally, self-reported screen time could introduce recall bias. Other factors that may affect sleep quality, such as stress levels, diet, and physical activity, were not controlled, limiting the generalizability of the findings.

References

- Walker MP. The role of sleep in cognition and emotion. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. 2009; 1156:168-97.
- Borbely AA. A two-process model of sleep regulation. *Hum Neurobiol*. 1982; 1(3):195-204.
- Grandner MA, et al. Sleep duration and risk of type 2 diabetes: a meta-analysis of prospective studies. *Diabetes Care*. 2010; 33(2):414-20.
- Buysse DJ, et al. The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index: a new instrument for psychiatric practice and research. *Psychiatry Res*. 1989; 28(2):193-213.
- Przybylski AK, et al. Electronic screen use and sleep in adolescents. *Pediatrics*. 2015;135(4)
- Cajochen C, et al. Evening exposure to a light-emitting diodes (LED)-backlit computer screen affects circadian physiology and cognitive performance. *J Appl Physiol*. 2011; 110(5):1432-8.
- Chang AM, et al. Evening use of light-emitting eReaders negatively affects sleep, circadian timing, and next-morning alertness. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*. 2015; 112(4):1232-7.
- Lemola S, et al. Adolescents' electronic media use at night, sleep disturbance, and depressive symptoms in the smartphone age. *J Youth Adolesc*. 2015; 44(2):405-18.
- Hysing M, et al. Sleep and use of electronic devices in adolescence: results from a large population-based study. *BMJ Open*. 2015;5(1)
- Exelmans L, Van den Bulck J. Bedtime mobile phone use and sleep in adults. *Soc Sci Med*. 2016; 148:93-101.
- Hershner SD, Chervin RD. Causes and consequences of sleepiness among college students. *Nat Sci Sleep*. 2014; 6:73-84.
- Zitser J, Allen IE, Falgàs N, Le MM, Neylan TC, Kramer JH, Walsh CM. Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) responses are modulated by total sleep time and wake after sleep onset in healthy older adults. *PLoS One*. 2022 Jun 24; 17(6):e0270095. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0270095. PMID: 35749529; PMCID: PMC9232154
- Nikolic A, Bukurov B, Kocic I, Vukovic M, Ladjevic N, Vrhovac M, Pavlović Z, Grujicic J, Kistic D, Sipetic S. Smartphone addiction, sleep quality, depression, anxiety, and stress among medical students. *Front Public Health*. 2023 Sep 6; 11:1252371. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2023.1252371. PMID: 37744504; PMCID: PMC10512032.
- Hale L, Guan L. Screen time and sleep among school-aged children and adolescents: a systematic literature review. *Sleep Med Rev*. 2015; 19:32-41.
- Wu X, Li D, Zhou X, Wang L, Chen Y. The association between screen time and sleep disorders in children and adolescents: a meta-analysis. *Sleep Med*. 2019; 59:1-9.
- Hirshkowitz M, Whiton K, Albert SM, Alessi C, et al. National Sleep Foundation's sleep time duration recommendations: final report. *Sleep Health*. 2015; 1(1):40-43.
- Custer E, Ailey S, Hegadoren K, et al. Screen time and sleep in children: a systematic review. *CNS Spectr*. 2019; 24(5):550-558.